

GEOTECHNICAL INVESTIGATION AND SLOPE STABILITY ANALYSIS OF THE RIGHT BANK OF ARIAL KHAN RIVER OF BANGLADESH

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INTRODUCTION

Geotechnical investigation is utmost important for any of the design of earthen structures. Such an important earthen structure is river bank which is slope in nature. However, slope instability is one of the major problems in geotechnical engineering. It is, therefore, essential to check the stability of slope. Arial khan is one of the biggest distributaries on the right bank of the Padma River. The river maintains a meander channel through its course and is erosion in nature (Padma River, Banglapedia). The river bank is somewhere very steep and somewhere is plain to flood plain. Bank protection is therefore, one of the prime necessities for human wellbeing. In light of that major point of view, this study has been undertaken at Sannyasir Char of Shibchar thana in Madaripur district.

METHODOLOGY

The geotechnical data have been collected from the study report of River Research Institute. The study area is located at Sannyasir Char of Shibchar thana in Madaripur district. The coordinates of the boreholes are at #BH-1 (E-204142.34&N-2590445.942), #BH-2 (E-204398.462&N-2590013.42), #BH-3 (E-203853.278&N-2590707.32), #BH-4 (E-203853.278&N-2590237.76), #BH-5 (E-203706.133&N-2590069.75) at the right bank of Arial Khan River from where soil samples have been collected. Field and laboratory investigation have been conducted for geotechnical investigation. Field investigation includes bank slope determination, SPT-N values, soil strata depth wise, ground level, ground and surface water level etc. Laboratory investigation several tests such as natural moisture content, grain size analysis, specific gravity, Atterberg's Limit, consolidation test, permeability test, tri-axial test and direct shear, unit weight etc., have been conducted. Bishop's Simplified Method and Janbu method have been used for slope stability analysis. The factor of safety of the assumed failure surface determined by the equation (1)

$$F_s = \frac{\sum \frac{1}{m_\alpha} [c' + (W - ub)\tan\phi']}{W \sin\alpha} \quad (1)$$

Where, $m_\alpha = (1 + \tan\phi' \tan\alpha / F_s) \cos\alpha$.

Figure 1: a) Slope stability-The Bishop method of slices, b) Study area

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The study area has been shown in the river map in Figure 1. The study results have been shown in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1: Showing the test results of cohesive and non-cohesive soils in the study area

Name of the parameters	Cohesive Soil	Non-cohesive Soil
Soil Density	Very soft to medium stiff	very loose to dense
Particle Sizes of Sand in %	16-48	31-99
Particle Sizes of Silt in %	51-83	1-67
Particle Sizes of Clay in %	1-5	0-2
Specific Gravity, G _s in %	2.680	2.670-2.672
Unit Weight in kN/m ³	18.22-18.44	17.83-17.99
Plasticity in %	9-21	
Cohesion	10-25	0-1
Angle of internal friction	20-30	27-32
Permeability in cm/sec	10 ⁻⁶ -10 ⁻⁴	10 ⁻⁴ -10 ⁻²
compression index	0.181-0.259	

Table 2: Safety factor of the different holes of Sannyasir Char

Location	Hole No.	Factor of Safety
Sannyasir Char	BH-1	1.28
	BH-2	1.88
	BH-3	1.65

Nuzhath Fatema and Mehedi Ahmed Ansary (2014) studied on an embankment at Basuria in Sirajganj near the bank of Jamuna River. They observed that grain size of the soil contains 63% sand, 35% silt and 2% clay. They found the maximum safety factor 2.255 for soil at dry condition with a slope 1:2 while the minimum factor is 0.66 at rapid drawdown condition with 1:1 slope. Md. Shofiul Islam et al (2014) worked on dry and wet in-situ soil sample in the laboratory for showing the major cause of bank erosion. They found that the soil samples are silty clay with friction angle 40° and 24° at dry and wet condition respectively.

CONCLUSION

The right bank of Arial Khan River at Sannyasir Char is more or less stable except boring hole no. 01. According to Bishop's Simplified Method and Janbu method the boring hole no.1 of Sannyasir Char is not stable and the bank is not safe (FS<1.5) at the coordinate E-204142.34 & N-2590445.942. The study results seem to meet up the design of stability of riverbank of Arial Khan River as geotechnical investigation is an utmost important engineering aspect for stability analysis and knowing the safety factor for appropriate measure.

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